

Szilard Engine and Classical Versus Statistical Single Particle?

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The Szilard engine example seems to be based on a single particle whose location may be measured like a classical particle, but then seems to behave in a statistical/thermodynamic manner. To quantify this statement, the ideal gas law $PV=nRT$ is used to compute work in (1) using: $\int nRT dV/V$. The idea seems to be that a reservoir supplies heat to keep T constant as the single particle, measured by a Maxwell demon to be on the left hand side of a container when a partition is added to the middle, as an isothermal expansion occurs until the container is back to size V . In such a case, entropy decreases in the reservoir and universe and heat is converted completely into work, violating the second law of thermodynamics.

We try to argue that there is a fundamental problem with this example and that is the mixing of the notion of a classical particle with a statistical one. We first point out that the ideal gas law is often linked with the usual maximization of entropy $\ln(N! / \prod_i n_i!)$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i n_i = N$, with Stirling's approximation being used. Stirling's approximation cannot be used unless there are a large number of particles, not one. If one considers this problem with a large number of ideal gas particles in a volume V at T , then the equivalent situation of finding a single particle on the left hand side when a partition is added to the middle is the process of pushing the gas back to the left half of the container while keeping T constant. This involves work $-W$ and heat gain of Q which exactly balances the work W and heat loss $-Q$ from the reservoir as the system expands toward the right hand wall. Thus, no net work is gained and there is no net loss of entropy, thus nullifying the Szilard engine argument.

An issue now arises with respect to a single particle. A main idea of statistical mechanics/thermodynamics is that a particle, even in a single one, may be found anywhere in V . Thus, having a demon (1) measure the particle to be in the left hand side breaks the notion of a statistical particle and replaces it with classical one. Even in the case of a dilute gas which thermalizes only through collisions with the wall, there is still equal probability for a gas particle to be anywhere in V (no potential) and so localizing a single particle which is said to represent the entire gas breaks the entire notion of statistical mechanics/thermodynamics. Thus, if the single particle is measured by the demon to be on the left hand side of the container, we argue that this means that it must have been pushed isothermally by a partition on the right hand side which moves to the center doing $-W$ work and obtaining Q heat. These two values must be used together with results from subsequent processes, i.e. the process of the single particle pushing the partition back to the right hand wall.

Szilard Engine

The Szilard engine, as described in (1), involves a single particle which essentially represents an entire ideal gas. This particle is in a box of volume V in equilibrium with a heat reservoir at temperature T . The idea is that a demon adds a movable partition to the center and measures that the particle is on the left hand side. The particle then quasistatically moves the partition in an isothermal manner. This requires a heat flow from the reservoir into the box. Work is done, but when the partition reaches the right hand wall, everything is back to the beginning except

that work has been gained and entropy lost from the reservoir. This violates the second law of thermodynamics.

Various approaches have been used to try to suggest that there are problems with the above analysis and that entropy does not really decrease. A main approach (1) is to try to deal with memory and measurement and tie it to entropy changes. A second approach (2) is to argue that the piston and the particle are statistical quantities and that the piston is large and has energy fluctuations and probably delivers more energy to the particle than vice versa. Thus, (2) concludes that the isothermal expansion does not occur.

We suggest that one has to consider the measurement (localization) of the single particle in the left hand side in a statistical manner and that this resolves the issues present.

An Ideal Gas with Many Particles

We first argue that ideal gas statistical mechanics, in particular the use of $PV=nRT$ in (1), implies many particles, not one. In particular, to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, one may maximize:

$$\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!) \text{ subject to } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) \text{ where } n(e_i) = Np(e_i) \quad ((1))$$

This leads to $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ if one approximates $\ln(n(e_i)!) = n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ which is Stirling's approximation and only holds for large $n(e_i)$. If there is no potential, then the N particles are distributed uniformly throughout V . This begs the question: What does it mean to find the entire gas on the left hand side of the container like the single particle in the Szilard engine? We argue that there is one way to achieve this and that is to introduce a partition along the right wall and push the gas isothermally and quasistatically until the partition is at the middle of the container. This requires:

$$-W \text{ work and the release of } Q \text{ heat, } ((2))$$

Now, one has the Szilard condition for the single particle on the left. The gas then does work W and the reservoir supplies Q heat, i.e. $-Q$ for the reservoir. Thus, overall work $(-W+W)=0$ and heat $Q-Q=0$. Overall there is no heat or work loss of gain and no violation of the second law of thermodynamics. In other words, there are two processes which must be considered, not the single one of the partition moving from the center to the right with a reservoir losing Q .

Single Particle Szilard Engine

This brings one back to the single particle Szilard engine. We have argued above that for a many-particle gas, one has to first do work and obtain heat to move the gas to the left hand side of the container before it can expand.

The idea of the Szilard is that a single particle may just happen to be on the left hand side, where it is measured by the demon. We argue that this is fine for a classical particle, but suggest that one must describe an ideal gas of N particles by a single particle and cannot violate the statistical properties being used.

A fundamental statistical property is that if there is no potential, then the gas has a uniform density. This is equivalent to a single particle having the same probability to be at position in the volume V . If a single particle is to represent the entire gas, then it cannot be localized on either the right or left we argue, unless it has been forced there by doing work and removing heat as in the many particle gas scenario presented in the previous paragraph.

Thus, we argue that the statement of the demon finding the particle on the left hand side of the box is immediately associated with $-W$ of work and Q of heat removed from the particle. One must take these into account when describing any further processes if the single particle is to behave in a thermodynamical manner, which is what seems to be implied by the Szilard engine. We thus argue that it is not just W done by the single particle isothermally moving the partition or $-Q$ heat loss from the reservoir, but again $W-W$ and $Q-Q$.

Thus, there is no violation of the second law of thermodynamics in this example, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the Szilard engine scenario, even though one deals with a single particle, it must retain all statistical properties of an entire ideal gas. The single particle cannot be found to be on the left hand side of the container by a demon by accident, only a classical particle can have this feature. If a statistical particle is on the left hand side, this means that a partition on the right hand side wall pushed the particle to at least the center quasistatically and isothermally doing W of work and obtaining Q of heat from the particle. Thus, one does not start with a particle in the left hand side and no work or heat and then argue that if the particle pushes a partition placed at the middle isothermally that all that is present is the work W done and the heat $-Q$ lost by the reservoir. The total work is $-W+W=0$ and the heat, $Q-Q=0$. There is no violation of the second law of thermodynamics. We argue that the single particle, treated as a statistical particle, must have the same features of an ideal gas of many particles. We note that formally statistical mechanics for an ideal gas requires many particles in order to use Stirling's approximation which appears in one kind of derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Even other approaches (reaction balance) which do not use Stirling's approximation, still implicitly use the notion of many particles.

To recap, a particle representing an ideal gas cannot simply happen to be localized in the left side of the container because this means viewing it as a classical particle and not a representation of an ideal gas which means that the particle can be anywhere. To say it is on the left hand side means that it has been pushed there, involving $-W$ and Q removal from the particle.

References

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